

TECHNIQUES OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: There are many different teaching strategies that you might implement with elementary-aged pupils. Since every approach uses a distinct set of tools and approaches to accomplish similar educational objectives, an approach that works for one instructor may not necessarily be helpful for another. Because of this, many teachers attempt to draw ideas from several teaching strategies, combining and blending them into one special teaching strategy depending on the needs of the students, the school, and other factors. In this article we have listed and made a review of the most popular approaches that might be useful for teachers.

Key words: focusing, repetition, game-tasks, creative work, innovative methods, add songs to our lesson, independent thinking.

Introduction: Number of people of any age learning English in recent times is increasing a lot. This is because living without knowing English in the process of life it's getting harder. But language learning also depends on age. Even scientists children have proven to acquire language faster and easier than adults. Language in children a natural tendency to learn, that they have a strong imitative character, children have more time than adults and quickly remember the information they have learned storage is one of the main reasons for this. Scientists to education, they believed that the approach through the game facilitates the educational process. Not only that not only makes it easier, but also increases the interest in this subject and allows the child to gain in-depth knowledge encourages. Game-style lessons help children develop oral speech will give. First graders are very good at visualizing a variety of pictures or videos they see From games in developing their speech through various colorful pictures should be used regularly. Primary education methods are slightly different from regular education methods, because primary school students are very young. The field of education is different abilities and students who work together with individuals are gathered together stands out as a dynamic environment and the task of teachers for each creative and to meet the personal needs of students effective teachers who are able to implement innovative

teaching strategies it is important to have. In this article, modern teaching of English in primary grades. As a result of the application of approaches and innovations methods, students are logical development of thinking skills, fluency of speech, quick and correct answers formation of skills, enthusiasm for knowledge, careful preparation for classes information about the aspiration is given.

Main body: English language grammatical understanding of language teaching to elementary school students it is necessary not to start with giving. Otherwise, from the first step of teaching a foreign language it can tire the child and weaken his interest in learning the language. Because it is difficult to teach a foreign language to elementary school students at the same time is one of the responsible tasks. That's why to primary classes from the following innovative methods to teach English meaningfully and interestingly can be used:

Student-Centered. The remaining strategies from this list are thought to be student-centered or constructivist when we explore moving the emphasis from instructor to students. The concept of a student-centered approach has gained popularity as society and the educational sector have developed, and there are strong reasons for this. Students are involved in the design, implementation, and assessments in student-centered classrooms. By involving the students in these choices, the instructor is less responsible and more ownership is transferred to the students. Teachers must also develop the confidence to go from a directive to a collaborative leadership style. While this is going on, kids are free to walk around the classroom, work in small groups, and visit centers.

Add songs to your lessons. Songs and nursery rhymes are one area on which I currently place a lot of emphasis with students in elementary school. If you get the chance to buy more books, I'd highly suggest Primary Music Box from Cambridge University Press. I learned about this tool through the British Council in Bucharest, Romania. It's a great, really wonderful book with a selection of classic nursery rhymes and educational games for young children. The "The Wheels on the Bus" picture matching activity—a fantastic activity for the transportation theme—is my favorite activity in this book. To locate appropriate nursery rhymes to play in the background while the students are working, you might also search YouTube.

Creative Projects. It's crucial to keep in mind that primary students do better when given more imaginative assignments like painting and drawing. I concentrated on subject vocabulary every day, but there was also always a creative activity to complete. Numerous glue sticks, cans of paint, drawings, and

colored pencils were used. In contrast to the conventional manner they may be used to in their own classes (sitting down and listening to the teacher lecture), the sheer act of cutting out or sticking can be highly enjoyable for the kids.

Embrace Training Young Learners. It appears to be plain sense, but many teachers frequently ignore it. You must genuinely like teaching young language learners if you want to be effective. At this age, primary young learners are still learning how to wield a pencil, how to use a pair of scissors, or even how to speak their first language, so you need to be mindful of that. So, my first piece of advice would be to make sure you enjoy working with young children.

Lesson Subjects. In the beginning, we mismatched the lessons we taught our primary-aged students (back in South Korea): some art, some vocabulary, and some activities. The lessons lacked coherence and had no clear subject. I soon learned that focusing on themes or subjects each day while integrating grammar and vocabulary into the lesson was the ideal strategy for dealing with elementary learners. Something that I now include in all of my classes for young learners and adolescents. Focusing on lesson topics has the advantage of helping students become more engaged, but you must select subjects that will hold the attention of students in the elementary grades, such as animals, body parts, or food. The contents list of any primary-aged materials and photocopyable resources will provide you with all the information you need.

Conclusion: Repetition or reinforcement of game-tasks during lessons it gives positive results if used in classes. Choosing a type of game-assignment to the type of lesson, students of the class are trained to perform games and tasks level, their level of knowledge, opportunities for independent creative work, what they have learned ability to quickly restore in memory depends on the level of creativity. In short, it is an obligation to teach language to elementary school students not as, but on the contrary, using interesting games and innovative methods to conduct, to serve as a foundation for the knowledge they will receive in the future possible.

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